

ISic0651

I.Sicily inscription 0651

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [- □ □ - □ □ - □ □] αὐτῷ τύμβο[ν- □]
2. [- □ | - □ □ - □ □ - - □ □] τῷδε τάφῳ
3. [- □ □ - □ □ - □ □ - □ □] ἐκ] διαθήκων
4. [- □ □ - □ □ - τὸστέφο]ς ἀμφέθετο
5. [- □ □ - □ □ - □ □ - ὀλίγη δό]σις υἱ[ῶ]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644891

PHI 332934

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité*. 106: 79-118. At 98 no.13 fig.18

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